

PARTICIPATION OF NATIONAL LEADERS IN THE COUNCIL OF PEOPLE'S SUPERVISORS OF THE USSR

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8394641>

Allanazarov Murot Mirzaevich

*is a senior lecturer at Termiz State University, doctor of philosophy (PhD) in history.
murodallanazarov00@gmail.com*

Abstract

In this article, the Council of People's Supervisors of the USSR, which is the executive body of the Authority, has taken into account the interests of not only the capital city Bukhara and its surroundings, but also the interests of all residents of the entire country. That is why there is a kind of harmony and agreement in the activities of central and local state and government agencies.

Key words

Central Committee, Economic Council, people's supervisor, modernist movement, district executive, Agriculture, educational system

The government of the People's Soviet Republic of Bukhara was called the Council of People's Supervisors. Like Bukhara Revkom, it was formed for the first time in August 1920, consisting of 9 members. Then the Emirate power was overthrown, and on September 14, 1920, at the general meeting of the People's Council of Supervisors, the Revolutionary Committee and the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Bukhara, a 9-member government was formed under the chairmanship of Fayzulla Khojaev - the Soviet of Supervisors of the USSR.

Among them, Faizulla Khojaev (chairman and foreign affairs supervisor), Qori Yoldosh Polatov (education supervisor), Abdulkadir Muhitdinov (land affairs supervisor), Mukhtarjon Saidjonov (internal affairs supervisor), Usman Khoja [Usmonhojaev] (finance supervisor), Najib Husaynov (state inspector of control), Yusuf Ibrohimov (chairman of the emergency commission), Mukammil Burkhanov (inspector of justice), Bahovuddin Shihabuddinov (inspector of military affairs). In some historical studies, some changes in the structure of the initial government are written as follows: Abdurahim Yusufzada (inspector of land affairs - agriculture), Mirzo Muhiddin Mansurov (inspector of trade and industry), Mirzo Isom Muhitdinov (inspector of food and nutrition) were introduced. The government was formed from progressives in Bukhara, that is, national leaders.

We would like to dwell on the activity of each of the 9 People's Observers, i.e. ministers, who were members of the initial government of the USSR headed by Fayzulla Khojaev.

Fayzulla Khojaev [son of Fayzullah Khoja Ubaydullahhoja] (1886-1938) - a well-known state and public figure, a prominent representative of the Jadidist movement in Bukhara, chairman of the Soviet of Supervisors of the USSR (1920-1924), chairman of the Central Revolutionary Committee of the Uzbek SSR (1924-1925), People's Commissar of the Uzbek SSR He worked in responsible positions such as the chairman of the Council of Ministers (1925-1937). Faizulla Khojaev showed the world a great example of serving the Uzbek people with his work.

In today's terms, Faizulla Khojaev was 24 years old when he became the Prime Minister of the USSR government. In the history of 20th century Uzbekistan and the world, such a unique Prime Minister will not be found again. F. Khojaev skillfully managed the government of the USSR for 4.5 years. He was 28 years old when he started to manage the government of the Uzbekistan SSR, and in this position he worked continuously for about 13 years. He sacrificed his personal life and sweet soul for the interests of the Uzbek people and Uzbekistan. In June 1937, the 7th session of the CP (b) of Uzbekistan was held. F. Khojaev chaired several meetings. F. Khojaev was bedridden for 3 days due to a heart attack. He went to work on June 21 and at the end of the working day signed the decision No. 840 of the Council of People's Commissars on current affairs. It became a document of the Government after he signed it. When the composition of the government of the USSR is written in documents, after the Prime Minister and the People's Inspector of Foreign Affairs, the surname of the People's Inspector of Education Polatov [Kori Yoldosh Polatov] comes. Kori Yoldosh Polatov (1890-1965) is one of the major representatives of the Jadidist movement in Bukhara. He was born in the city of Karki in the family of an Uzbek scholar. Studied at Mir Arab Madrasa. He opened and taught New Methodist schools. He was the head of the Karki branch of the Young Bukhara faction (since 1912).

After the establishment of the USSR, Kori Yoldosh Polatov was the People's Inspector of Education (1920-1922), People's Inspector of Internal Affairs (1922), People's Inspector of Finance and Chairman of the Bukhara Economic Council (Ekoso) (1922-1923). At the request of Moscow, in June 1923, he was removed from the government of the USSR and exiled from Bukhara.

Kori Yoldosh Polatov, together with Fitrat and Fayzulla Khojaev, did great work in organizing the education system in the Bukhara People's Soviet Republic, sending 70 young people to study in Germany and Turkey.

Abdulkadir Muhitdinov worked as the People's Inspector of Land Affairs [Agriculture] in the first government.

In the initial list of government members given by F. Khojaev, the People's Inspector of Internal Affairs Mukhtar Saidjonov (1893-1937) stands third. Mukhtar Yoldoshevich Saidjonov is also a major representative of the Jadidist movement in Bukhara. Born in Bukhara. He studied in Bukhara madrasas. From 1917, he was a member of the Central Committee of Young Bukharas. After the Kolesov Incident (March 1918), Yosh broke away from the Bukharas and joined the Communist Party of Bukhara.

After the overthrow of the Emirate government in Bukhara, Mukhtar Saidjonov became the People's Inspector of Internal Affairs of the USSR (September 1920-May 1921; March 1922-August 1923), People's Inspector of State Control (November 1920-May 1921), a special representative of the USSR under the government of the RSFSR worked in responsible positions such as representative (May 1921-March 1922), responsible secretary of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Bukhara (December 1921-1923), responsible secretary of the Central Executive Committee of the USSR (August 1923-October 1924).

After national-territorial demarcation was carried out in the Central Asian republics in the fall of 1924, Mukhtar Saidjonov worked as the chairman of the Zarafshan district executive committee and secretary of the party committee (1925).

People's Inspector of Finance Usman Khoja [Usman Khojaev; Usmonkhojaev; Osmankhoja Polathoja's son] will be discussed later.

Najib Husainov (1885-1937) was the inspector of state control, Yusuf Ibragimov (1895-1961) was the chairman of the Extraordinary Commission.

Mukammil Burkhanov, the People's Inspector of Justice, occupies a special place in the government of the USSR. Mukammil Burkhanov is a well-known representative of the Jadidist movement in Bukhara, a state and public figure.

The list of government members (eighth in the first composition, ninth in the second composition) is completed by the People's Inspector of Harbiya [Military Affairs] Bahoviddin Shahobiddinov (1892-1920).

Abdurahim Yusufzada (1880-1937) was a well-known representative of the Jadidist movement in Bukhara. After the establishment of the Soviet Union, Abdurahim Yusufzada was the deputy chairman of the revolutionary committee of the Chorjoi region, the People's Inspector of Agriculture (Land Affairs) of the Soviet Union (1920-1921), the Ambassador of the Soviet Union to Afghanistan (1921-1922), the People's Inspector of Justice (1922-1923), the People's Inspectorate of

Foundation Affairs under the Ministry of Education. worked as the chairman of the special commission on

After the overthrow of the emirate regime in Bukhara, Mirzo Muhyiddin Mansurov worked as the People's Inspector of Trade and Industry of the USSR (1920-1921).

At the II Congress held in September 1921, the composition of the Bukhara Council of People's Inspectors (10 inspectorates) was formed as follows.

1. Faizulla Khojaev - chairman and foreign affairs inspector.
2. Abdulkadir Muhitdinov - economic inspector.
3. Father (Otaulla) Khojaev - the inspector of internal affairs.
4. Yusuf Ibrohimov - supervisor of land and water affairs.
5. Abdulhamid Arifov - military affairs inspector.
6. Kori Yoldosh Polatov - education supervisor.
7. Hashim Shayik - financial supervisor.
8. Rahmat Rafiq - the inspector of justice.
9. Hakimov - inspector of labor and social security.

10. Mukhtar Saidjonov - national management staff began to work in the positions of state control inspector.

The policy of each country depends on the quality and weight of modern personnel and qualified specialists. In the social, political and cultural life of the Bukhara People's Soviet Republic, the activities of local personnel at various levels of management occupy an important place.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. Tursunov, Zhovli Narzullaevich. "The Contribution of the Southern Regions to the Economy of Uzbekistan During 1970-1980s." *European Journal of Humanities and Educational Advancements* 2.5 (2021): 186-188.

2. Пардаев, Тошкентбой Ражабович, and Жавли Нарзуллаевич Турсунов. "САНОАТДА МАҲАЛЛИЙ МУТАХАССИСЛАР ТАЙЁРЛАШГА ТАРИХИЙ НАЗАР." *ВЗГЛЯД В ПРОШЛОЕ* 26 (2019).

3. Пардаев, Тошкентбой Ражабович, and Жавли Нарзуллаевич Турсунов. "МУСТАБИД ТУЗУМНИНГ МИЛЛИЙ ВА ДИНИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРГА МУНОСАБАТИ." *ВЗГЛЯД В ПРОШЛОЕ* 23 (2019).

4. Турсунов, Жовли Нарзуллаевич. "Трудовой подвиг населения Сурхандарьинской области в годы Второй мировой войны." *Вестник науки и образования* 24-1 (102) (2020): 31-34.

5. TURSUNOV, ZHOVLI NARZULLAEVICH. "STAGES OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN AFTER THE SECOND WORLD WAR." THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCE Учредители: Теоретическая и прикладная наука (Тараз) 9 (2021): 311-313.

6. Турсунов, Ж. Н. "История экономического и социального развития городов Узбекистана (на примере городов Байсун, Шаргун, Шурчи). 1971-1990." Автореф. дисс.... кан. ист. наук. Самарканд, Институт археологии при Академии наук Узбекистана (1995).

7. Razhabovich, P. T., and T. Z. Narzullaevich. "A LOOK INTO THE HISTORY OF THE PREPARATION OF LOCAL PROFESSIONALS IN THE INDUSTRY." Ўтмишга назар журнали 26.2 (2019).

8. Pardaev, T. R., and Z. N. Tursunov. "THE ATTITUDE OF THE DESPOTIC REGIME TO NATIONAL AND RELIGIOUS VALUES." Ўтмишга назар журнали 23.2 (2019).

9. Юсупович, Қўшоқов Сафарали. "ЗАРДУШТИЙЛИК ДИНИ ТАЛҚИНИ ВА УНИНГ МОДДИЙ МАДАНИЯТДА АКС ЭТИШИ." Scientific Impulse 1.12 (2023): 246-251.

10. Isaev, O. A. "The Categories of Early Farmers Residing in the Surkhan Oasis in the 20-30s of the 20th Century." European Journal of Learning on History and Social Sciences 1.1 (2023): 108-111.

11. Isaev, O. A. "The Categories of Early Farmers Residing in the Surkhan Oasis in the 20-30s of the 20th Century." European Journal of Learning on History and Social Sciences 1.1 (2023): 108-111.

12. Oybek, PhD Isaev. "In the Study of the History of Surkhandarya in the 30s of the XX Century, as a Historical Source." Eurasian Journal of History, Geography and Economics 7 (2022): 100-102.

13. Isaev, O. A. (2021). From the Memories of Those Displaced as a Result of the Policy of Resettlement in the 1920-1930s of the XX Century (On the Example of the Surkhandarya Oasis). CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HISTORY, 2(10), 62-65.

14. Tukhtaev, Abdugani K. "The Role of Tourism in the Surkhandarya Oasis." International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding 9.1 (2022): 169-172.

15. Tukhtaev, Abdugani K. "The Role of Free Economic Zones in the Economy of Uzbekistan." International Journal of Social Science Research and Review 5.1 (2022): 1-4.

16.Тухтаев, Абдугани Киличович, and Бахтияр Сатторович Сафаров. "ВЗГЛЯД НА ИСТОРИЮ МИРОВЫХ ДЕНЕГ." Вестник науки и образования 24-1 (102) (2020): 35-38.

17.Тухтаев, Абдугани Киличович. "Роль сельского хозяйства в экспортном потенциале Узбекистана." Бюллетень науки и практики 6.10 (2020): 174-178.

18.Турсунов, С., and А. Тўхтаев. "Жарқўрғон." Т.: Фан (2008).

19.Kushokov , S. (2023). EARLY RELIGIOUS SIGNS OF THE TERRITORIES OF UZBEKISTAN. Research and Implementation, 1(3), 71-77

20.Yusupovich, Kushakov Safarali. "ORTA OSIYODA ILK DINIY QARASHLARNING OZIGA XOSLIGI." Scientific Impulse 1.11 (2023): 115-120.

21.Yusupovich, Kushakov Safarali. "FACTORS WHICH ARE THE BASIS OF THE FIRST RELIGIOUS VIEWS." Scientific Impulse 1.11 (2023): 140-145.

22.Ramazanovich, M. N., & Abdunazarovich, P. B. (2021). Protection of Family and Youth in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Middle European Scientific Bulletin, 18, 221-223.

23.Расулов Ҳ. Сиёсат-маданият, ҳодиса ва фан сифатида //Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 7. – С. 691-702.

24.Расулов Х. М. Шарқ ва ғарб: сиёсий ва ҳуқуқий маданият компонентлари уйғунлиги //ВЗГЛЯД В ПРОШЛОЕ. – 2020. – №. SI-1№ 3.

25.Расулов, Ҳ. М. (2022). СИЁСИЙ МУНОСАБАТЛАРДА СИЁСИЙ МАДАНИЯТ. Academic research in educational sciences, 3(NUU Conference 2), 863-867.

26.Rasulov, H. M. (2021). ELECTION PHENOMENON I THE PROBLEM OF IMPROVING THE ELECTRIC CULTURE OF THE POPULATION. ВОСТОЧНО ЕВРОПЕЙСКИЙ НАУЧНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ, 75(part 6), 28.

27.Mina, Simona. "Political decentralization and promoting participative culture, solutions in counteracting the financial global crisis." Managerial Challenges of the Contemporary Society 2 (2011): 176-180.

28.Расулов Ҳ. М. СИЁСИЙ МУНОСАБАТЛАРДА СИЁСИЙ МАДАНИЯТ //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. NUU Conference 2. – С. 863-867.

29.Расулов Х. М. ТЕХНОЛОГИИ ОБЪЯСНИТЕЛЬНО-РЕПРОДУКТИВНОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ //Актуальные проблемы гуманитарных и естественных наук. – 2020. – №. 3. – С. 45-49.

30. Zokirov, S. I., Sobirov, M. N., Tursunov, H. K., & Sobirov, M. M. (2019). Development of a hybrid model of a thermophotogenerator and an empirical analysis of the dependence of the efficiency of a photocell on temperature. *Journal of Tashkent Institute of Railway Engineers*, 15(3), 49-57.

31. Горовик, А. А., & Турсунов, Х. Х. У. (2020). Применение средств визуальной разработки программ для обучения детей программированию на примере Scratch. *Universum: технические науки*, (8-1 (77)), 27-29.

32. Ramazanovich, N. M. (2022). IMPORTANCE AND ANALYSIS OF THE CONCEPT OF CIVIL RIGHTS. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(10), 322-328.

33. Ramazanovich, M. N., & Kabilovich, B. O. (2021). Constitutional and Legal Framework for Providing International Peace. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 18, 218-220.

34. Mallaev, N. R., & Djalilov, S. S. (2021). Political and Legal Mechanisms of the Fight against Corruption in Uzbekistan and High Effective Measures against It. *International Journal of Development and Public Policy*, 1(7), 1-4.

35. Mallaev, N. R., & Djalilov, S. S. (2021). Establishment of Legal Mechanisms in the Fight Against Corruption in Uzbekistan. *European Journal of Life Safety and Stability* (2660-9630), 12, 4-8.